

DEVELOPMENT OF SOLAR POWERED FLOATING WASTE COLLECTION SYSTEM

Mr. Sreehari VS S¹, Mr. Sujith Kumar S², Mr. Vedanth P³ Mr. Yashwanth Raj⁴, Prof. Jagadeesh L.R^{*1}

^{1,2,3,4}UG Scholars, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University,

^{*1} Associate Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University.

ABSTRACT

The proposed work emphasis on design and fabrication of the river waste collecting system. Many of the rivers in India also many parts of the world filled with large quantity of man-made waste and garbage. The government of India has started an initiative of cleaning rivers and water bodies through “Namami Gange”, “Narmada Bachao” and many major and medium projects in various cities like Ahmadabad, Varanasi etc. Manuel cleaning is not much effective, hence automated cleaning system including robots are used for cleaning activities. Effort has been made to design and develop automated river cleaning system operated with solar energy to collect floating waste in the water.

Keywords: Waste collection, Solar Energy, Floating system

1. INTRODUCTION

Waste water is one of the common and major issue in major cities which produced from homes, business industries, commercial activities and institutions etc,. Before releasing into water bodies this water has to treat through treatment plants then it has to be released through pipes. Some of the cities in India treating the water in efficient way and releasing in to water bodies through well connected water drainage system. But one of the major issue in India disposal of waste directly in to water bodies without segregation. Specifically the rivers closed to the temples facing threat from dumping of religious items like flowers, incense sticks, plastic bottles and plastic covers. Unscientific way of disposing of water bottles and plastic covers is the one of the major problem in most of the places which results in blockage of sewage pipe in turn over flow of sewage water out of the passage some time leads to flood during rainy days. Accumulation of debris in the river affects the aquatic life and disturb the photosynthesis process of the aquatic plants by blocking solar radiation. Hence it is necessary to control disposal of debris or polluting of

water bodies by debris by collecting the debris before reaching the water body by using proper filtering techniques and collecting the debris from the water body by adopting appropriate technology so that surrounding ecosystem can be restored.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various techniques and devices are using to remove the debris from the water. Many researchers proposed various techniques to clean the water. M. Mohamed Idhris et.al [1] developed remote-controlled sewage cleaning machine to enhance the effective cleaning of water bodies. Abhijeet and his team [2] developed

efficient and effective solution for removing debris and pollutants from rivers. Mr. P. M. Sirsat.et.al [3] also discussed about development of innovative design for river cleaning. Pankaj Singh Sirohi.et.al [4] have discussed various advanced methods and technologies for river cleaning and highlighted strength, weakness and area's for improvement in advanced river cleaning technology. Ndubuisi c. Daniels [5] was developed drainage cleaning system for clogged and polluted drainage systems. Osiany Nurlansa.et.al [6] developed automatic garbage collector (AGATOR) robot for garbage collection. Basant Rai[7] done a study on pollution level and conservation efforts done on river ganga in India. This importance of this study to create awareness and provide insights for future cleaning strategies. Emaad Mohamed H.et.al [8] developed multi robot system for cleaning of marine oil spill in marine environment. N.G.Jogi and his team [9] developed pedal operated boat for garbage collection. This model is cost effective and environmental friendly. Ankita B.Padwal.et.al [10] discussed various methods adopted by earlier researchers on manually controlled drainage cleaning systems.

3. DEVELOPMENT FLOATING WASTE COLLECTION SYSTEM.

To develop the floating waste collection device the following methodology(fig 1) has been adopted.

Fig 1: Methodology Used

The proposed work is to develop the machine is to lift the waste debris from the water surface and dispose them in the tray. Here we are fabricating the remote operated river cleaning machine. The collecting plate and chain drives are rotating continuously by the motor. The collecting plate is coupled between the two chain drives for collect the waste materials from river. The collected wastages are thrown on the collecting tray with the help of conveyer. Our project is having propeller which is used to drive the machine on the river. The propeller is run with the help of two PMDC motor. The total electrical device is controlled by RF transmitter and receiver which use to control the machine remotely. The fig 2. shows the schematic drawing showing of the system.

Fig 2: Front and side view of model

Two hulls and waste collection bin was fabricated using 22 gauge GI sheet. Two propellers were made of ABS material manufactured using 3D printing technology. The supporting structure was welded as per the design. Four motors of different specifications have been used to operate water wheels and also for operating conveyor belt and garbage collector. ESP8266 micro controller was used to control all the mechanism of the device. 10 Watt solar panel along with 12V battery were used to supply the required. IR controlled 8 channel relay board is used to operate the system remotely. The complete assembled view of the floating waste collection system is shown in fig 3.

Fig 3: Photograph of the assembled model

The system was tested in the water body with real time functioning. All the components are working as per the requirement and system is able to collect debris in the water like plant leaves, plastic covers and other floating wastes in the water.

4. CONCLUSION

The floating waste collection system is designed and fabricated as per the specification. The testing results are satisfactory even though it is smaller version. It is able to collect debris like leaves, plastic covers and small empty plastic water bottles.

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